

International Journal of Managing Public Sector Information and Communication Technologies(IJMPICT)

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Scope & Topics

The International Journal of Managing Public Sector Information and Communication Technologies (**IJMPICT**) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles that contribute new results in regards to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the public sector around the world. ICT are becoming fundamental to the operation of government agencies, especially in light of the development of e-government applications and rising citizen expectations. As such, the International Journal of Managing Public Sector Information and Communication Technologies (**IJMPICT**) seeks to establish new collaborations, new best practices, and new theories in public sector organizations around the world in regards to developing, applying, managing, measuring, monitoring, procuring, and securing ICT in governmental operations (including civilian, military, health care and education applications). The journal thus provides a platform to disseminate new ideas and new research, advance theories, and propagate best practices in the management of ICT in public sector organizations at the international, national, state/provincial and local levels. The International Journal of Managing Public Sector Information and Communication Technologies (**IJMPICT**) offers a forum in which academics, consultants, and practitioners in a variety of fields can exchange ideas to further research and improve practices in all areas of governmental operations and ICT strategies.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and organizational experiences that describe significant advances in information and communication technologies in governmental organizations.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Accessibility
- Adoption and diffusion of technology
- Analysis
- Biometrics
- Budgeting
- Change management
- Cloud computing
- Citizen services
- Citizen participation
- Computer-mediated communication
- Content development
- Cyber-crime and cyber-terrorism

- Cyber public relations
- Data warehousing
- Data mining
- Digital divide
- Digital government
- Digital libraries
- Digital rights management
- ERP
- Education, training courses, and curricula
- Emergency and disaster response management
- e-Governance (Electronic Governance)
- e-Government (Electronic Government)
- e-Learning (Electronic Learning)
- e-Payments (Electronic Payments)
- e-Publishing (Electronic Publishing)
- e-Taxation (Electronic Taxation)
- e-Voting (Electronic Voting)
- Electronic Data Interchange (EDI)
- Electronic healthcare
- Electronic records
- Enterprise architecture
- Evaluation
- Geographic information systems (GIS)
- Group decision support systems (GDSS)
- Health care
- Identity management
- Immigration issues
- Impacts/implications
- Implementation issues
- Information access and availability
- Information management
- Information preservation
- Information security
- Infrastructure
- Innovation
- Intelligent agents
- Intelligent systems
- Intelligent organizations
- Inter-agency information sharing
- Internet
- Knowledge management
- Knowledge networks
- Law enforcement
- Legal and regulatory issues
- Management of technology
- m-Government (Mobile Government)

- Mobile applications and services
- Multimedia applications
- Open source
- Online auctions and technologies
- Online education and learning
- Organizational and human factors
- Organizational culture
- Peer-to-peer social networks
- Political issues
- Poverty
- Protocols and Standards
- Public administration
- Public participation
- Privacy
- Records retention
- Reengineering
- RFID (radio frequency identification)
- Rural issues
- Shared services
- Social networks
- Strategy
- Storage issues
- Stakeholder issues
- Supply chain issues
- Trust
- Ubiquitous Computing
- Universal access
- Urban issues
- Value chain issues
- Virtual Reality
- Web 2.0
- Workforce issues

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail ijmpict@airccse.org. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : June 09, 2018**
- Notification : July 09, 2018
- Final Manuscript Due : July 16, 2018
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief